

20:5 n-3	5.28 ± 0.23^a	5.35 ± 0.31^a	5.44 ± 0.07^a	5.10 ± 0.41^a	0.5406
22:5n-3	1.38 ± 0.07^a	1.34 ± 0.08^a	1.37 ± 0.04^a	1.37 ± 0.12^a	0.9384
22:6 n-3	11.32 ± 0.81^a	10.87 ± 0.73^a	11.36 ± 0.38^a	10.47 ± 1.47^a	0.6292
